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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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THE ROLE OF INSTRUCTIONAL SCAFFOLDING IN DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS AMONG EFL UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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Abstract: This study examines the effectiveness of instructional scaffolding in developing critical thinking skills among university students learning English as a Foreign Language (EFL). The relevance of the research is associated with ongoing reforms in higher education in Uzbekistan and the growing need to foster independent, analytical, and creative thinking among students. A mixed-methods research design integrating quantitative and qualitative approaches was employed.

The study involved 84 undergraduate students from Uzbekistan State World Languages University and the National University of Uzbekistan. The experimental group was exposed to multi-level scaffolding strategies, including graphic organizers, problem-based learning tasks, and metacognitive questioning techniques, whereas the control group followed conventional instructional practices.

The findings revealed significant improvements in the experimental group's ability to analyze information, construct evidence-based arguments, and evaluate alternative solutions. Furthermore, students demonstrated higher levels of communicative engagement and academic autonomy. The results confirm that systematic implementation of instructional scaffolding and gradual withdrawal of pedagogical support (fading) contribute substantially to the development of higher-order thinking skills in EFL learning environments.

Key words: instructional scaffolding, critical thinking, EFL students, Zone of Proximal Development, higher education, pedagogical support, autonomous learning, Uzbekistan.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot ingliz tilini chet tili sifatida o'zlashtirayotgan (EFL) oliy ta'lim talabalari orasida tanqidiy fikrlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda pedagogik qo'llab-quvvatlash (instructional scaffolding) metodologiyasining samaradorligini aniqlashga qaratilgan. Tadqiqotning dolzarbligi O'zbekiston oliy ta'lim tizimida amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlar hamda talabalarda mustaqil, tahliliy va ijodiy fikrlash kompetensiyalarini shakllantirish zarurati bilan izohlanadi.

Tadqiqotda miqdoriy va sifat tahlillarini uyg'unlashtirgan aralash metodologik yondashuv qo'llanildi. Amaliy-pedagogik tajribaga Toshkent davlat jahon tillari universiteti va O'zbekiston Milliy universitetining bakalavriat bosqichida tahsil olayotgan 84 nafar talaba jalb etildi. Tajriba guruhida grafik organayzerlar, muammoli-izlanishli topshiriqlar hamda meta-kognitiv savollar asosida ko'p bosqichli scaffolding strategiyalari joriy etildi. Nazorat guruhi esa an'anaviy o'qitish usullari asosida ta'lim oldi.

Yakuniy natijalar tajriba guruhi talabalarida axborotni tahlil qilish, argumentlarni asoslash va muqobil yechimlarni baholash ko'nikmalari sezilarli darajada rivojlanganligini ko'rsatdi. Shuningdek, talabalarning kommunikativ faolligi va akademik mustaqilligi oshgani aniqlandi. Tadqiqot natijalari EFL darslarida scaffolding strategiyalarini tizimli qo'llash hamda talaba mustaqilligi ortib borishi bilan pedagogik ko'makni bosqichma-bosqich kamaytirish (fading) muhim ekanligini tasdiqlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: instructional scaffolding, tanqidiy fikrlash, EFL talabalari, Yaqin rivojlanish zonasi, oliy ta'lim, pedagogik qo'llab-quvvatlash, mustaqil ta'lim, O'zbekiston.

Аннотация: Данное исследование посвящено изучению эффективности педагогической поддержки (instructional scaffolding) в развитии навыков критического мышления у студентов высших учебных заведений, изучающих английский язык как иностранный (EFL). Актуальность работы обусловлена реформированием системы высшего образования Узбекистана и необходимостью формирования у студентов самостоятельного, аналитического и творческого мышления.

В исследовании использован смешанный методологический подход, сочетающий количественные и качественные методы анализа данных. В педагогическом эксперименте приняли участие 84 студента бакалавриата Узбекского государственного университета мировых языков и Национального университета Узбекистана. В экспериментальной группе применялись многоуровневые стратегии скаффолдинга, включающие графические органайзеры, проблемно-поисковые задания и метакогнитивные вопросы. Обучение контрольной группы осуществлялось традиционными методами. Полученные результаты показали значительное улучшение у студентов экспериментальной группы навыков анализа информации, аргументации и оценки альтернативных решений.

Кроме того, отмечено повышение коммуникативной активности и академической самостоятельности обучающихся. Результаты исследования подтверждают, что систематическое использование технологий педагогической поддержки и постепенное снижение объема помощи преподавателя (fading) способствует эффективному развитию критического мышления в процессе обучения английскому языку как иностранному.

Ключевые слова: instructional scaffolding, критическое мышление, студенты EFL, зона ближайшего развития, высшее образование, педагогическая поддержка, автономное обучение, Узбекистан.

INTRODUCTION

The contemporary global higher education landscape requires universities to reject the outdated role of mere knowledge repositories. Within English as a Foreign Language (EFL) instruction, developing language proficiency is no longer viewed as an isolated goal; instead, it is directly integrated with higher-order cognitive processing, particularly critical thinking ^[1]. For undergraduate students, participating in academic discourse using a foreign language creates a dual cognitive demand: they must simultaneously manage complex foreign language structures and actively analyze, synthesize, and evaluate abstract concepts ^[2].

In Uzbekistan, this educational shift has gained significant institutional support. Recent state decrees and strategic educational initiatives designed to update higher education stress the importance of preparing independent, analytically capable professionals. However, a noticeable teaching gap continues to persist: a large percentage of secondary school graduates entering universities are accustomed to teacher-centered, rote learning systems where memorization is prioritized over critical evaluation ^[3]. When these students encounter university-level EFL tasks—such as writing analytical essays or participating in structured academic debates—they often experience cognitive overload. This strain typically results in weak arguments, superficial textual analysis, and an underdeveloped academic voice.

To resolve this operational challenge, the framework of instructional scaffolding offers a valuable theoretical and practical solution. Developed from Lev Vygotsky's constructivist model of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), scaffolding involves the temporary, flexible support structures provided by an educator or an advanced peer. These supports enable learners to complete complex tasks that they cannot yet handle independently ^{[4], [5]}.

LITERATURE REVIEW

While the connection between educational scaffolding and language learning is well-documented, there is a clear shortage of empirical research investigating how specific scaffolded tools (such as conceptual, meta-cognitive, and procedural frameworks) directly impact distinct critical thinking sub-skills within non-Western EFL environments like Uzbekistan. International scholars like Gibbons ^[6] and Walqui ^[7] have studied scaffolding thoroughly in Western settings, but applying these techniques within the specific curriculum structures of Central Asian universities requires deeper investigation. Similarly, local researchers such as Bahranova ^[8] and Jalolov ^[9] have highlighted the need to modernize modern EFL methodologies, yet practical, systematic designs for integrating cognitive support frameworks into everyday language skills development remain limited.

Research gap and novelty of this study bridges a distinct gap in current educational literature: the lack of experimental data regarding how structured pedagogical scaffolding affects specific critical thinking components (analysis, inference, and evaluation) among EFL university students in Central Asia. The innovation of this study centers on designing and executing a culturally and contextually adjusted Scaffolding Matrix for Uzbek undergraduate students. This matrix offers a structured system for tracking cognitive development as

students move from highly guided language tasks toward complete academic independence. EFL undergraduate students exposed to systematic instructional scaffolding will display statistically significant improvements in their overall critical thinking scores compared to peers exposed to conventional teacher-centered instructions. Specific dimensions of critical thinking, namely Cognitive Analysis and Argument Evaluation, will respond more robustly to procedural and conceptual scaffolding than the dimension of Inference.

Research design of this study used an integrated, mixed-methods quasi-experimental design conducted over an 8-week period during the spring academic term. Quantitative information was gathered using standardized pre- and post-intervention critical thinking tools. Qualitative data was collected through semi-structured focus group discussions, focusing on the students' actual experiences regarding their cognitive load and developing independence.

Participants and context of the sample included 84 third-year undergraduate students majoring in Philology and Foreign Language Education at two major public universities in Tashkent, Uzbekistan. The participants belonged to two pre-existing academic cohorts, which were randomly assigned to either the Experimental Group or the Control Group Age bracket: 19–22 years. Language baseline: Intermediate to Upper-Intermediate English fluency (CEFR levels B2.1 to B2.2), confirmed by internal university placement data. Homogeneity: A Levene's test for equality of variances showed no significant baseline differences in language ability or critical thinking competencies between the groups prior to starting the study. Intervention Framework: The Scaffolding Matrix

METHODOLOGY

The control cohort received standard, textbook-based EFL instruction that targeted basic reading comprehension and essay writing through teacher-led discussions. In contrast, the experimental cohort interacted with a structured Scaffolding Matrix organized into three progressive developmental phases:

Macro-Phase 1: High Scaffolding (Conceptual Focus - Weeks 1-2): The instructor directly demonstrated critical thinking strategies. While examining academic texts, the educator used think-aloud protocols to model how to identify subtle biases, unstated assumptions, and flaws in logic. Students used highly structured Graphic Organizers (such as Venn diagrams and Toulmin argument models) to visually separate different elements of a text.

Macro-Phase 2: Medium Scaffolding (Metacognitive Focus - Weeks 3-5): Direct modeling by the teacher was gradually decreased. The instructor added Metacognitive Prompts and open-ended question stems adapted from Bloom's Revised Taxonomy (e.g., "What specific data supports the author's primary conclusion, and what counter-arguments are missing?"). Students worked in pairs using reciprocal teaching methods to evaluate each other's reasoning.

Macro-Phase 3: Fading and Autonomy (Procedural Focus - Weeks 6-8): External instructional supports were systematically removed (faded). Students worked with unedited, authentic socio-cultural texts, requiring them to write analytical argumentative essays and manage peer reviews based on minimal criteria rubrics. The responsibility for building and testing arguments shifted fully to the learners.

Instruments and data analysis - Quantitative Assessment: A contextually adapted and validated version of the California Critical Thinking Skills Test (CCTST) was used for the pre- and post-tests. This instrument assessed three primary sub-scales: Analysis, Evaluation, and Inference with a maximum possible score Qualitative Tool: Two post-intervention focus group were held with participants. The discussions were recorded, fully transcribed, and analyzed using thematic coding. Statistical Processing: Data analysis was carried out using SPSS v.26. The analysis included descriptive statistics, paired-samples t -tests for internal group changes, and independent-samples t -tests for differences between the groups, with Cohen's d utilized to measure effect size.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Results of the empirical information collected after the 8-week study showed measurable differences between the groups. Table 1 summarizes the comparative statistical data from the pre-test and post-test assessment periods for both the Control Group (\$CG\$) and the Experimental Group (\$EG\$).

Table 1: Statistical Breakdown of Pre- and Post-Test Critical Thinking Sub-Scales

Critical Thinking Dimension	CG Pre-test Mean (SD)	CG Post-test Mean (SD)	EG Pre-test Mean (SD)	EG Post-test Mean (SD)	Cohen's d (EG)
Analysis (Max: 10)	5.12 (1.14)	5.34 (1.08)	5.08 (1.21)	8.24 (0.85)*	1.14
Evaluation (Max: 10)	4.88 (1.32)	5.02 (1.25)	4.94 (1.28)	7.91 (0.91)*	0.98
Inference (Max: 10)	4.54 (1.05)	4.81 (1.11)	4.61 (1.14)	6.12 (1.02)*	0.45
Total Score (Max: 30)	14.54 (3.51)	15.17 (3.44)	14.63 (3.63)	22.27 (2.78)*	1.21

* Denotes statistical significance at the $p < .001$ level.

Qualitative themes from focus groups - thematic coding of the focus group interview notes revealed three central psychological and cognitive themes: Reduction of Cognitive Overload: Students noted that visual frameworks, such as argument maps, reduced the cognitive stress of handling unfamiliar language alongside complex concepts. One student shared: "Initially, dealing with an 800-word academic text in English felt overwhelming. But when our teacher separated it using argument maps,

I stopped focusing on the difficult vocabulary and started evaluating the primary arguments." Internalization of Scaffolding Prompts: Over the course of the study, students began using the instructor's questioning strategies naturally during peer interactions without direct teacher guidance. Stress Reduction and Confidence Building: The predictable sequence of the instructional phases reduced classroom anxiety, offering students a reliable roadmap during open-ended academic debates.

The quantitative and qualitative outcomes of this study support using instructional scaffolding as a primary tool for cognitive development in EFL learning environments. The noticeable improvements in the experimental group's critical thinking metrics demonstrate that cognitive skills can be systematically built through well-structured pedagogical interventions.

These outcomes align with and build upon Vygotsky's constructivist models [6]. By introducing carefully balanced instructional supports within the Zone of Proximal Development, the intervention successfully bridged the gap between the students' current language limitations and the complex reasoning expected at the university level. The high growth in the Analysis and Evaluation components matches the findings of global educational researchers like Al-Noreen [10], who observed that visual organizers help students isolate specific claims and recognize underlying structural patterns more easily.

Importantly, the varying speeds of growth across different cognitive sub-skills add detail to existing scaffolding theories. The slower progress seen in Inference shows that reading between the lines and drawing logical conclusions from indirect text requires deep cultural and semantic familiarity with the language. As a result, while procedural supports can quickly improve a student's ability to evaluate and map out textual arguments, inferential skill seems to develop more slowly, connected tightly to long-term language exposure and vocabulary depth [11].

In the context of higher education in Uzbekistan, these results offer a practical alternative to traditional, lecture-based instructional routines. Many local EFL classrooms still rely heavily on grammar translation and memorization exercises, which prioritize rote learning over deep interaction [3]. This study demonstrates that Uzbek undergraduate students adapt successfully to student-centered, scaffolded learning spaces. The organized, step-by-step design of the scaffolding matrix offered the academic security required for students to leave passive learning habits behind and build analytical independence with confidence.

CONCLUSION

Analytical synthesis of This empirical study demonstrates that instructional scaffolding serves as an essential teaching strategy for improving critical thinking skills among university EFL students. The research successfully validates hypothesis showing that a structured scaffolding matrix results in a statistically higher increase in analytical abilities compared to conventional teaching practices. Additionally, hypothesis was confirmed, showing that while evaluative and analytical skills develop quickly through procedural supports, inferential logic follows a longer, more gradual developmental timeline.

Practical recommendations for higher education institutions are based on these findings, the following actions are suggested for university EFL programs in Uzbekistan: curriculum realignment: shift away from isolated grammar and vocabulary drills. Integrate language acquisition directly with cognitive expansion by organizing learning units around problem-solving tasks that feature systematic scaffolding. Systemic use of visual tools: integrate visual frameworks (such as Toulmin argument structures and conceptual hierarchy maps) during the initial phases of reading academic texts and organizing essays.

Faculty training initiatives: implement professional development workshops for university educators focusing on scaffolding practices. Teachers should learn both how to establish instructional supports and how to systematically remove them (fading) to encourage student independence. Balanced assessment policies: update grading rubrics to ensure that final assessments evaluate analytical depth, logical reasoning, and evidence validation alongside standard grammatical and lexical accuracy.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.